

THE ROLE OF FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract : This article provides information on the nature of the digital economy, its level of development in other developed countries, and explains the objective necessity of the transition of all sectors of our country to the digital economy in the current globalization situation, and the special role of financial technologies. attempted.

Key words : Financial technology, **hashing** , digital economy, internet, mobile network communications, business, "information society".

Inter:

Remains an extremely urgent issue that cannot be delayed for all countries and, of course, economic entities . There are many definitions of digital economy in the scientific literature and press pages, including in foreign sources, digital economy is defined as the interconnection between digital information technologies and economic agents, and in others, it is defined as the connection of economic entities with the Internet. As a result of economic development, there are some definitions of activities related to the creation, distribution and use of digital technologies and related products and services. There are other definitions of the digital economy. Indeed, such definitions of the digital economy accurately represent its essence, since it is appropriate, but not sufficient, to consider the digital economy as a development process linked to technologies and economic agents or the Internet. first of all, it is connected with the development of digital information technologies and ensuring the development of socio-economic

directions of all countries. For this reason , it would be more complete if the digital economy is defined as the provision of economic and social development as a result of the introduction and effective use of modern information technologies in all sectors of the national economy of each country and various aspects of social life. we count. The digital economy is not limited to electronic commerce, production of goods and services related to information technologies , but also health care, science and education, construction, energy, agriculture and water resources of the national economy. It is rapidly entering the fields of agriculture, transport, geology, cadastre, archive, internet banking, social and law enforcement, and high efficiency is ensured in each of them. Undoubtedly, the emergence and development of digital information technologies is an objective process arising from the demand of society's development . Creating and using new information technology systems is an opportunity to meet existing needs. In this case, all users actively participate in the promotion of digital information technologies. Today, digital information technologies are focused on mass and rapid processing of information. They should help managers make wise decisions, protect themselves from possible surprises of a changing market , create the necessary conditions to ensure competitiveness, and ultimately achieve success. At present, the most popular and widespread technological tools for the development of digital information technologies are the Internet.

Analysis of the literature on the topic: When talking about this topic, we can take SS Gulyamov's work "Blockchain technologies in the digital economy " as a scientific basis. This guide is currently up to speed dedicated to the emerging field of digital economy and describing its infrastructure. In it issues related to the underlying problems of the digital economy , some of the hashing functions that are an important element of the cryptography of the digital economy system information provided. After that, the logic of the transition from cryptography to digital currencies, cryptocurrencies the main types and their properties are described. To attract investments in various

projects The concept of ICO used and its scope are shown.

Methods of conducting research: Digital economy is considered an area with a growing trend today. Taking this into account, in the implementation of the research, it is necessary to analyze financial and blockchain technologies in a systematic manner in the context of the digital economy, and to create an opportunity to study the strategic and mutually beneficial processes in the implementation of the main goals and tasks in them. we used the mutual comparison method.

Analysis: According to calculations, the transition to the digital economy will allow to increase the labor productivity of the companies operating in the national economy of the country, their work efficiency, increase in production, ensure the transparency of the activity, increase the absolute amount of the product and sharply reduce its cost. will give. This is his greatest advantage. Using the digital economy , quality service is provided to consumers, buyers and clients and a number of other conveniences are created. This includes ordering lunch, calling a taxi, sending money to a distant neighbor , cross-border business cooperation, e-commerce space, remote office. The introduction of digital technologies and its rapid development have already become the main priorities for a number of countries. They are distinguished by the long duration of the implementation period of digital development, the continuity of priorities, starting from the creation of basic information and communication technologies, the formation of an acceptable policy in this area and the support of programs for the wide implementation of digital technologies. 2 trillion per year as a result of the digital economy in twenty countries that are currently leading the world ranking. Additional funds are being created in the amount of US dollars . It is estimated that their implementation will allow to increase labor productivity in companies by 40% and the gross domestic product by at least 30%. At the same time, it will be an obstacle to overwriting, the rise of the underground economy, and the

spread of similar vices . As our President Sh.M.Mirziyoev emphasized, he will prevent and eliminate the evil of corruption while ensuring a high level of economic growth. On the basis of the wide introduction of the Internet system in our country, in the transition to the digital economy, in connection with the further development of the forms of communication of individuals and legal entities with state bodies, the new version of the "Uniform interactive state services" portal, Uzbekistan

The launch of the virtual lobby of the Prime Minister of the Republic for consideration of businessmen 's applications - "business.gov.uz" portal can be considered as the beginning of important events. So, along with some positive developments regarding the transition to the digital economy in our country, there are also enough issues that are waiting to be resolved. As the President noted, "Although our country rose by 8 places in 2019 according to the international information and communication technology development index , we are still far behind. If we say that most ministries, agencies, and enterprises are completely far from digital technologies, this is also true." As our head of state noted, "Of course, we know very well that the formation of the digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. But no matter how difficult it is , if we don't start it today, when will we start it? Tomorrow will be too late . Therefore, active transition to the digital economy will be one of our top priorities in the next five years . Our country has great natural resources. It is natural that their efficient and effective use also serves to ensure economic growth. For example, in the current era of globalization, the development of the countries of the world no longer depends only on their natural resources or geographical location. This makes it necessary to pay special attention to the issue of ensuring the organic cooperation of state bodies and business entities on the introduction of innovative ideas, technologies and developments, and the cultivation of personnel with deep knowledge of modern knowledge and

intellectual potential. So, there are enough problems in the wide implementation of the digital economy in our country. The adoption of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" Program, approved by the Presidential Decree in October of this year, will undoubtedly serve as a programmatic solution. In conclusion, we considered it appropriate to quote the following thoughts of the founder of Microsoft Corporation, Bill Gates, who is a well-known person in the field of information technology: "Soon there will be only two types of companies on the planet: the first, those who do business on the Internet, and the second , companies out of business". This shows that the transition of all countries to the digital economy is the need of the hour.

Summary and offers : Rapid implementation of digital information technologies in national economic sectors and all aspects of the social sphere is a priority issue for all countries. Today, the digitization process, which is taking place rapidly, has created a "new economy", that is, a digital economy . This little-studied and deeply rooted economy creates great opportunities for producers to organize effective marketing activities in entrepreneurship and social spheres, reduce costs to a minimum, get maximum profit, sell goods and provide services successfully. In recent years, a new generation of digital information technologies has appeared in entrepreneurship and other socio-economic activities on a global scale, and due to the scale of their development, in science "artificial intelligence", "robotics", "Internet of things", "wireless technologies" and other terms appeared. These are all elements of the digital economy. The long-term spread of information technologies in the world has determined the development paths of the national economy of countries, caused fundamental changes in people's lives, and laid the foundation stone for the emergence of the term digital economy in science. This is to develop the national economy of each country at an optimal level and thereby ensure the material well-being of the people.

List of used literature.

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on January 24, 2020. // People's Word, January 25, 2020, issue 19.
2. Utkin VB , Baldin KV Information systems and technologies in the economy. - Study guide (in Russian). - M.: UNITI, 2018.
3. Jumanova S. Digital economy: the path to development.//New Uzbekistan, 2020